

DataCite StrainInfo Metadata Analysis

Authored by	Sara El-Gebali
Reviewed by	Stephanie Hagemann
Contributions by	Torsten Kahlert
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About

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Related Documents

- [Primary Metadata Report](#)
- [Secondary Metadata Report](#)

Background

The initial phase of this project is dedicated to establishing a comprehensive understanding of the persistent identifier (PID) landscape within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

This effort is led by PID4NFDI, a collaborative initiative involving DataCite, the Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen (GWDG), the Helmholtz Open Science Office, and the Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology. The consortium works closely with experienced PID infrastructure users to leverage their insights and amplify the impact of PID adoption within NFDI workflows.

This report outlines the foundational phase, which encompasses use-case analysis, requirements engineering, and concept development. These activities are designed not only to address immediate project needs but also to ensure that the insights gained facilitate seamless integration and ongoing development in future project phases.

As part of our deliverables for the initialization phase work packages 1 and 2, this use-case analysis serves several key purposes:

- **Work Package 1 (WP1):** This encompasses deliverable **D1.1**, which focuses on exploring the landscape of PID practices across different NFDI services, and deliverable **D1.2**, which involves a requirements analysis of selected use cases to derive practical and relevant insights. These analyses set the stage for a broader understanding of how PIDs are implemented and managed across diverse research contexts within NFDI.
- **Work Package 2 (WP2):** Within WP2, deliverable **D2.1** aims to develop a conceptual framework for mapping selected use cases to existing PID services. The goal here is to ensure that our understanding of use cases

translates into actionable strategies for integrating PID services effectively across NFDI consortia.

Criteria for Use-Case Selection

The selection of use cases was a crucial step in ensuring a diverse and representative analysis. We established the following criteria for choosing which use cases to examine:

1. **Diversity in duration of operation and PID service providers:** We aimed to reflect a range of maturities, encompassing both well-established and newer initiatives. This variety helps us understand PID usage at different stages of project development and their engagement with different stakeholders (i.e., PID Providers).
2. **Disciplinary Breadth:** The use cases needed to span multiple disciplines to assess the adaptability and versatility of PID adoption across different scientific fields and sectors.
3. **Active Engagement:** The use cases had to demonstrate active contributions and engagement.

Use-Case Analysis: StrainInfo

On the basis of the aforementioned criteria, the service **StrainInfo**¹—operated by Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH and part of the NFDI4Microbiota consortium—was selected as a use-case to demonstrate effective management of PIDs for microbial strains.

StrainInfo fulfills the following criteria:

- **Maturity:** StrainInfo is an established system that actively mints Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) using DataCite services, making it an ideal candidate for examining established PID practices and understanding the complexities of long-term PID management.
- **Data Connectivity and Diversity:** StrainInfo collects and connects distributed data, matching microbial strain identifiers from multiple databases. This

¹ <https://straininfo.dsmz.de/>

includes culture collection numbers, sequence accession numbers, and DOIs, providing a cohesive mechanism to bridge different types of metadata across repositories.

- **Disciplinary Variety:** The DSMZ is involved in multiple initiatives, including NFDI4Microbiota and NFDI4Biodiversity, and participates in international networks such as de.NBI, DZIF, GFBio, ELIXIR, and GBIF. This cross-disciplinary engagement provides an excellent opportunity to observe PID utilization across various scientific fields, ranging from microbiology to biodiversity research.
- **Confirmed Engagement:** The contact person and project lead for StrainInfo, Lorenz Reimer, has confirmed his commitment to this project, ensuring an ongoing, collaborative relationship. Furthermore, his group is a member of the NFDI PID Working Group, indicating active involvement in PID-related discourse and initiatives.

StrainInfo Background

Cataloging microorganisms is inherently complex, as each newly cultivated species must be deposited in at least two international culture collections, each assigning its own unique identifier. Persistent identifiers are therefore essential for maintaining traceability and connectivity across these diverse databases. The Leibniz Institute DSMZ's central registry for strain identifiers addresses these challenges by integrating data from multiple collections, enhancing both research reliability and data management practices. By centralizing these data points, StrainInfo not only simplifies the tracking of microbial strains, but also serves as a model for unifying distributed and diverse data through persistent identifiers.

In the long term, the aim is to establish a new central registry for microbial strains that offers persistent identifiers independent of culture collections. This vision seeks to provide a universal system that can be applied to any microbial strain, further enhancing data integration and research capabilities across the scientific community.

For more information about StrainInfo's work and their future plans, please refer to the report of the 2024 PID4NFDI stakeholder workshop ².

² PID4NFDI (2024). PID4NFDI Stakeholder Workshop Report. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14232461](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14232461)

Results

The results of our analysis of StrainInfo are grounded in a multistep evaluation process that combines qualitative and quantitative methods, starting with a **preliminary analysis** of their metadata in **March 2024**. As a DataCite Member, the metadata that StrainInfo submits in DataCite services through DOI registration is deposited under a CC0 license, which significantly enhances discoverability and ensures broad accessibility by the research community. This foundational analysis provided an initial snapshot of metadata quality and the completeness of information submitted by StrainInfo.

Following the preliminary findings, we conducted a **meeting** with the StrainInfo team to understand their current practices and gather detailed feedback. This direct engagement was invaluable for identifying gaps, challenges, and areas where improvements were needed.

In **November 2024**, we performed a **secondary analysis** of their metadata. This follow-up enabled us to assess changes that had been implemented as a result of our initial conversations. We noted several improvements, including enhanced metadata quality and greater alignment with recommended best practices. This iterative feedback loop proved effective in achieving tangible progress.

Additionally, the StrainInfo team participated in a **structured survey**³, providing valuable feedback on their experiences and challenges, as well as suggestions for improvement. This enabled us to compare StrainInfo's responses with those of other NFDI consortia, helping us evaluate whether the insights and assessments drawn from StrainInfo as a use-case effectively reflect the broader needs and challenges faced across the consortia landscape.

Finally, we conducted an **in-depth interview** with the StrainInfo team to delve deeper into the specifics of their processes and their vision for PID4NFDI in the long term. The interview provided rich qualitative insights, further clarifying the rationale behind their strategies and their approach to scaling PID implementation.

³ Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14277479](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479)

Comparative Metadata Analysis Before and After Stakeholder Meeting

As part of our evaluation process, we conducted a comparative analysis of StrainInfo's DOI metadata both before and after our direct engagement. This comparison provided insights into the effectiveness of our recommendations and highlighted areas of significant improvement.

Core information on StrainInfo's DataCite repository:

- Member of DataCite Consortium managed by ZB MED (Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin - Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften)
- Provider of DOI registration repository: Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures
- Number of DOIs registered: 290,106 registered in September 2023
- Number of DOIs updated: 306,291 in June 2024
- DOI Prefix: 10.60712
- Timeframe for Comparison:
 - **Before:** March 1, 2024
 - **After:** November 12, 2024

Main Outcomes

We provided two reports to the StrainInfo team, each of which included a metadata completeness check. These checks function as diagnostic tools to evaluate how effectively a repository or service meets DataCite's standards and adheres to best practices. The reports offer insights into the organization's performance in registering comprehensive metadata, identifying potential gaps. Additionally, they help uncover patterns and trends in metadata submission, providing actionable recommendations to enhance metadata quality.

Our comparative analysis of the two reports reveals strong metadata health across both mandatory and recommended fields, with a few exceptions. The "RelatedItems" field was deemed not relevant to the dataset, while the optional fields "GeoLocation" and "Contributors" presented specific challenges. "GeoLocation" was not applicable to the domain, and the "Contributors" field faced limitations due to difficulties with the

retrospective registration of contribution attribution information, which is discussed further in this report. Overall, the metadata completeness and quality, as depicted in the figure below, underscore the repository’s dedication to maintaining essential metadata attributes, facilitating efficient data discovery, and promoting interoperability.

Figure 1: Completeness of Metadata Elements – Primary vs. Secondary Analysis. Metadata properties are categorized by **Mandatory**, **Recommended**, and **Optional**.

Figure 2: Analysis of optional properties. Size and Format attributes have been updated.

Growth in DOI Registrations: The total number of registered DOIs grew from **290,106** to **306,291**, reflecting an increase of **16,185** additional DOIs.

The increase included registering new DOIs for 16,185 entries that were part of the originally registered DOIs. Specifically, this involved updating the metadata of these DOIs and assigning new identifiers to reflect version changes (e.g., from version 1.0 to version 2.0). However, it is important to note that this approach is not universally required, as DataCite offers the following guidelines⁴:

- **For minor content changes**, the same DOI can be used with updated metadata, and assigning a new DOI is not necessary.
- **For major content changes**, a new DOI is recommended, with the new DOI linked to the previous one through related identifiers.

The distinction between minor and major changes depends on the specific use case and can vary in interpretation. This topic is explored in more detail in later sections.

The metadata updates focused on schema improvements and alignment. StrainInfo updated its metadata to comply with **version 4.5** of DataCite’s Metadata Schema,

⁴ DataCite Versioning Guidelines : <https://support.datacite.org/docs/versioning>

incorporating several enhancements in metadata completeness based on our discussions. For instance, fields such as size and format, previously 100% missing, were updated to be 100% present.

These updates, implemented in June 2024, are tracked by DataCite's provenance system, which records the metadata history of DOI records. This system provides detailed information about what changes were made, when they occurred, and by whom. Provenance data, accessible via an API, has been systematically captured for all DOI registrations since March 10, 2019⁵.

Figure 3: Number of Findable DOIs registered each year.

Related Identifier Updates: The newly registered identifiers were linked back to their original counterparts using related identifiers as illustrated in Figure 4 and Table 1, reflecting a key outcome from our discussions with the StrainInfo team resulting in maintaining a coherent connection between versions of their content. This demonstrates an active and effective use of PIDs in metadata management to ensure continuity and traceability.

⁵ [DataCite Tracking Provenance Documentation](#)

Figure 4: Related Identifiers growth before and after.

Table 1: Metadata completeness comparison before and after updates. “Related Identifiers Completeness” reflects the percentage of missing or added related identifiers. “Related Identifier Type (DOI)” specifies the number of properly linked DOIs. Relation types (“IsPreviousVersionOf” and “IsNewVersionOf”) denote how DOIs are linked to represent versions. The improvements highlight efforts to enhance metadata accuracy and traceability.

Category	Before Updates	After Updates
Related Identifiers Completeness	99.9% of related identifiers were missing	89% of related identifiers were missing (10% improvement, 32,084 added linked identifiers)
Related Identifier Type (DOI)	Only 63 DOIs were specified	32,084 DOIs were now properly linked
Relation Types: IsPreviousVersionOf	42 DOIs	16,053 DOIs
Relation Types: IsNewVersionOf	21 DOIs	16,032 DOIs

Meeting Report: Key Findings and Challenges

Our meeting with StrainInfo stakeholders provided valuable insights into their current PID practices and highlighted specific challenges they face in registering DOIs that align with StrainInfo's specific requirements. The discussion shed light on both technical and procedural hurdles. The feedback from these stakeholders provided a clearer understanding of their priorities, as well as areas where targeted support or improvements could enhance their DOI registration process.

1. **Mass Submissions and Bulk Handling:** One of the key issues discussed was the need for a better bulk submission tool, ideally via the API, to handle large datasets efficiently. StrainInfo managed to process about 300,000 submissions in roughly 9 hours using a few optimizations, but they stressed the importance of improving tools for large-scale submissions, especially when assigning many DOIs during version updates.
2. **Data Format Validation:** There was also a problem with inconsistent data format validation during submissions, particularly for JSON data. Errors sometimes slipped through and were only found after registration, highlighting the need for stronger validation protocols to catch issues earlier in the process.
3. **Documentation Gaps:** Stakeholders felt that current JSON documentation was lacking, particularly when compared to XML, making it more challenging for new users. This clearly showed a need to improve documentation resources so that contributors can get started more easily.
4. **Cost Considerations:** Stakeholders were also concerned about the long-term sustainability of PID registration. While funding from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) through NFDI4Microbiota is currently covering the costs, it is unclear who will bear these expenses once the project ends. They stressed the importance of developing sustainable funding models to support PID registration in the future.
5. **Metadata Enrichment and Relationship Mapping:** StrainInfo shared their ongoing efforts to map relationships among cultures, strains, related works, and organizations. They are actively enriching metadata to make these connections clearer. One challenge they highlighted was that many publications cite samples only at the culture collection level rather than the

individual strain level, something they want to improve by making metadata more detailed.

6. **Retrospective Registration and Contributor Attribution:** StrainInfo deals with a lot of retrospective registrations, which complicates contributor attribution. Contributors to older datasets are seldom documented formally, affecting metadata completeness. This is an area that requires better solutions to ensure equitable and accurate attribution.
7. **Formats and Geolocation Metadata:** StrainInfo do not include geolocation information as it is not relevant for their data.
8. **Future Plans:** Looking ahead, StrainInfo plans to expand their harvesting activities to find new strains, register a few thousand strains directly, and update existing records (which was performed in June 2024). Their motivation for using DOIs remains rooted in sustainability and promoting reuse in the community, with metrics like citations and downloads seen as crucial to gauge impact.
9. **Revitalization of StrainInfo:** StrainInfo originally ran in Belgium until 2016, when funding ended. It was later revitalized at DSMZ. Stakeholders stressed that demonstrating the impact of their work through citation analysis will be crucial for securing further funding by showcasing research reuse and overall impact.

These insights helped us better understand the practical needs and challenges faced by StrainInfo. The discussions covered both technical issues such as data validation and documentation, and strategic concerns such as funding and metadata enrichment. Addressing these areas will be key to improving StrainInfo's ability to manage microbial strain data effectively and sustainably.

Survey

DSMZ, as an active member of the ZB MED DataCite consortium, plays a crucial role in PID management by registering DOIs and supporting infrastructure-related services. They are a Consortium Organization, fully participating in PID4NFDI initiatives. From the PID4NFDI project, they expect:

- Guidance on best practices for PID implementation.

- Facilitation of NFDI cross-consortium collaborations.
- Development and harmonization of shared PID standards and policies.
- Joint efforts in formulating PID standards and guidelines.

Infrastructure and Data Management

DSMZ oversees key infrastructures that facilitate both resource sharing and data analysis, specifically:

- **StrainInfo** (URL: <https://straininfo.dsmz.de/>): Released approximately one year ago, StrainInfo aims to enhance microbial strain data sharing, focusing on efficient resource utilization.
- **BacDive** (URL: <https://bacdive.dsmz.de/>): A mature data platform focused on microbiological data, offering robust tools for analysis and data processing.

These platforms are custom-built, using in-house software solutions and various relational databases (e.g., MariaDB) to meet their unique needs.

Current Phase of PID Integration and Metadata Practices

DSMZ is currently in the prototype phase of PID integration for certain services, with less than a year into the process.

They register over 10,000 PIDs annually and report high satisfaction with DataCite services.

DSMZ employs multiple metadata schemas within their repositories, such as:

- DataCite Metadata Schema
- Schema.org
- Bioschemas.org

In addition, they have adopted DataCite's metadata connection standards, such as using *relatedIdentifier* and *nameIdentifier*, which enables effective linkages among related research outputs.

Key Decision Factors for PID Membership

When deciding on PID memberships, DSMZ considers the following:

- **Alignment with Organizational Needs and Technical Compatibility:** These are highly influential factors, emphasizing technical feasibility and alignment with institutional goals.
- **Community Recommendations and Peer Influence:** Recommendations from the research community hold some influence, indicating peer feedback also informs their decisions.
- **Costs and Ease of Integration:** Cost-effectiveness and integration simplicity are practical considerations impacting PID service choices.

Outreach and Community Engagement

DSMZ actively engages with the research community to promote PID awareness through:

- **Online Webinars and In-person Conferences:** Aimed at educating researchers on the value of PIDs.
- **Social Media Engagement:** Channels like X (formerly Twitter), Bluesky, and Mastodon are used to reach a broader audience.

They have expressed a need for more specialized onboarding materials, webinars, and low-threshold information to enhance outreach.

Challenges in PID Implementation and Governance

DSMZ identified several challenges in guaranteeing the sustainable management of PIDs:

- **Limited Staff Resources:** A significant barrier to effective PID management, indicating a pressing need for more dedicated personnel.
- **Integration with Existing Systems:** Integrating PID services into current workflows with community-specific issues and path-dependencies—for example, regarding metadata requirements or data provision and sharing practices—remains challenging.
- **Adapting to Evolving Standards:** Keeping up with changing PID standards and technologies presents an ongoing challenge.

Seeking Assistance and Future Training Needs

To address some of these challenges, DSMZ has sought external technical assistance, particularly around API issues and integration with DataCite services. They have also participated in DataCite training sessions, including webinars on PID fundamentals, and expressed interest in further training, specifically in metadata standards and API use.

In summary, the detailed responses, representing both NFDI4Biodiversity and NFDI4Microbiota, offered deep insights into their operations. The alignment between DSMZ's detailed feedback and the broader survey results confirms that DSMZ is an excellent use-case for examining PID adoption and integration across NFDI consortia.

Interview

The qualitative interview conducted in November 2024 provided direct insights to needs, challenges, and expectations, and enabled a deeper understanding of context-specific requirements and pain points.

- **NFDI Initiative:** StrainInfo is fully developed under NFDI funding, building on a legacy service with global usage.
- **Use-Case Value:** Serves as a model within NFDI for database design, integration, metadata management, and PID usage. The database has already

begun influencing other NFDI services through its demonstration of robust APIs and its focus on strain-specific identity management.

- **Interactions:** BacDive aggregates structured research data across a wide spectrum of microbial strains, whereas StrainInfo specializes in accurately identifying and maintaining strain identities.
- **Persistent Identifiers:** Utilizes DOIs, ORCID iDs, and ROR IDs for comprehensive researcher and institutional traceability.
- **Metadata:** There are ongoing discussions about schema limitations (e.g., Schema.org and Bioschemas.org) and the potential development of a new microbial data exchange standard.
- **Interoperability:** It remains a core goal to enhance metadata interoperability via incorporating additional identifiers and enriching metadata fields.
- **Data Ingestion Challenges:** Relies on labor-intensive catalog data scraping from various sources, often lacking APIs or centralized databases. While systematic scraping allows for updates, it is sometimes dependent on obtaining permissions from catalog providers.
- **Technical Challenges:** Initial registration of 300,000 records required extensive planning to address API rate limits and avoid disruption. Scalable workflows now support ongoing updates.
- **DOI Versioning Guidelines:** Small changes, such as correcting typographical errors, may require new DOI assignments if they alter dataset integrity. Standardized guidelines are being developed to distinguish between updates and new registrations.
- **User Engagement and Feedback:** There was limited initial feedback, with plans now to expand their user base through targeted outreach. They are developing a researcher-driven registration platform linked to ORCID iDs and ROR IDs.
- **Future Directions:** Planned initiatives include a researcher-driven registration platform, metadata enrichment, and the development of a microbial data exchange standard.

Summary and Next Steps

The use-case analysis of StrainInfo provides valuable insights into the practical applications of PIDs for managing microbial strain information. The findings from this phase are instrumental to refining our understanding of PID practices, pinpointing areas for improvement, and guiding subsequent development activities.

The insights from the integration phase grant application further emphasize the role of use cases like StrainInfo as blueprints for documenting best practices during the ramp-up phase of PID integration. The focus of support will include:

- **Improving Metadata Quality:** Conducting metadata health checks to ensure compliance with standards and to enhance the completeness of metadata records.
- **Addressing Documentation Challenges:** Tackling specific challenges such as enhancing the documentation for JSON use.
- **Cross-Consortium Knowledge Sharing:** Facilitating opportunities for StrainInfo to connect with other use-case projects to share insights and experiences, potentially through collaborative events or workshops.
- **Hands-On Training:** Offering practical, hands-on training sessions focusing on API usage, and metadata quality and management.
- **Specialized Onboarding Materials and Outreach:** Developing more specialized onboarding materials, including webinars and accessible, low-threshold information to improve outreach efforts.
- **Support in Annotation and Data Interpretation:** Providing support for the annotation of specific data types, such as samples (with support from DataCite's IGSN ID expertise), and helping document their interpretation to ensure consistency and accuracy.